

EXPERIENCES OF DEVELOPED FOREIGN COUNTRIES RELATED TO INTERROGATION AS AN INVESTIGATIVE ACTION

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Abstract: The article analyzes the legislative and practical experiences of developed foreign countries regarding interrogation as an investigative action. The author compares the practices of Germany, France, Great Britain, and the USA, examining the protection of witnesses' and suspects' rights, the recording of their testimonies, the use of audio and video recordings, as well as tactical methods employed during interrogation. Some legal mechanisms absent in national legislation are considered through foreign examples, and recommendations are provided for adapting them to Uzbekistan's criminal procedure system.

Keywords: interrogation, investigative action, foreign experience, criminal procedure legislation, witness, suspect, audio-video recording, judicial practice, international experience, legal reforms.

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